

Prisoner in My Homeland

Developed by: Thirteen; The WNET Group; PBS and Electric Funstuff

Article contributed by: Alina Burmeister

Keywords

Abuse, Civil Rights, Empathy, Ethical Decision-making, Ethical Dilemmas, Forced Displacement, Japanese American Incarceration, Law, Migration, Population Expulsions, Racial Injustice, U.S. History

Figure 1. Screenshot from *Prisoner in My Homeland* (Thirteen; The WNET Group; PBS; Electric Funstuff). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the original creators.

Introduction

This point-and-click adventure game follows Henry Tanaka, a fictional 16-year-old Japanese American boy during World War II. Designed for middle school students, the game is an immersive role-playing experience that fosters historical perspective-taking and critical

thinking. After Japan attacked Pearl Harbor in 1941, President Roosevelt's Executive Order 9066 forced Henry's family and over 120,000 other Japanese Americans to leave their homes. They have to relocate from the family's strawberry farm on Bainbridge Island to an incarceration camp in Manzanar, California.

Players step into Henry's shoes, make decisions, and see how their choices shape his story. The game combines history with interactive learning, encouraging discussion and deeper exploration through additional resources. The game is part of the Mission US game series, developed in 2020 by Thirteen, the WNET Group, PBS, and Electric Funstuff, in collaboration with historians, educators, and the Japanese American community.

Facts

Release date:	2020
Developer:	Thirteen; The WNET Group; PBS and Electric Funstuff
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	Single player
Format:	Asynchronous
Time frame:	90 min–2 h
Languages:	English
Environment:	Computer or tablet
Material:	300 pages of educational material are provided online
Price:	Free of charge

Resonance & Criticism

Mission US is a widely recognized educational game, with over four million registered users across the U.S. and beyond (The WNET Group, n.d.). The game has been highly praised by both players and experts, earning notable prizes for "Prisoner in My Homeland," including the 2021 Japan Prize for Best Work in the Digital Media Division and a Gold Medal in the K-12 Education Category at the 2021 International Serious Play Awards.

Game Principle & Process

The game is divided into a prologue, three chapters, and an epilogue, each displaying a different part of Henry's journey as he adjusts to life in a Japanese American internment camp. In the prologue, the player learns how to navigate the world and select options. Players guide Henry through the camp, completing tasks such as taking a job, attending school, and prioritizing activities like sports or camp duties.

Social interaction is a key element, as Henry interacts with other non-player camp residents (NPCs), each offering diverse perspectives and experiences. Players receive feedback through badges, such as "Community Builder" or "Questioning Authority," which reflect their choices

and shape the story's outcome. There are no right or wrong choices to make (Schrier et al., 2024). Additionally, they expand their vocabulary by collecting key terms in a personal organizer, reinforcing historical and cultural learning throughout the game.

Activities like the decision tracker, mission reflections, and document analysis enhance understanding of the motivations behind historical events. Before each chapter, students can be given a decision tracker and a reflection sheet to note the decisions they make, why they make them, and how these choices affect the story. The teacher is advised to remind students to reflect on their values and the outcomes of different decisions before making them, to foster empathy and understand the complexity of decision-making.

The students should take a few notes after each decision and reflect on whether they would have made it if they were in Henry's situation, or whether a Japanese American teenager in the 1940s would have made it.

After going through the decision tracker, the students are given the mission tracker, in which they must explain the story's content and their impressions of the camp or its characters.

These tools allow students to test their knowledge and reflect on the values shaping their decisions in the game.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

By immersing players in historical scenarios, the game fosters historical empathy, which is defined as "...where we get to when we have successfully reconstructed other people's beliefs, values, goals, and attendant feelings" (Ashby & Lee, 1987, p. 63). It also develops critical thinking skills by encouraging players to analyze historical evidence and think like historians.

To achieve these goals, the game integrates structured educational tools. Teachers are provided with 300 pages of supporting materials, including clearly defined learning objectives, a curriculum outline, and timelines for each chapter. These resources also include historical background information to help the educator prepare for potential questions and discussions.

The teacher's role is supportive yet flexible. The game suggests walking through the prologue together in class, where teachers can explain the historical context and game mechanics. After this initial session, students can play independently, either in the classroom or at home, reducing the need for constant teacher involvement. The provided resources ensure educators can confidently guide their students without requiring extensive preparation.

Effectiveness

Research on serious games provides valuable frameworks for understanding the effectiveness of Mission US as an educational tool. Bruner's (2009) concept of situated cultural contexts emphasizes that learning occurs within specific cultural settings, utilizing relevant cultural resources. This aligns closely with Mission US, which immerses players in the historical

struggles for freedom, democracy, and equality, encouraging them to adopt the perspectives of ordinary people in the past. Implementing primary sources like photos, diaries, and documents expands the player's experience. This approach encourages critical thinking and mimics historians' work, such as analyzing evidence, identifying bias, and interpreting causality (Schrier et al., 2010).

The game achieves a high level of immersion through goal-based, narrative-driven gameplay that places the player in control of Henry Tanaka's emotional and physical journey, aligning with Lachlan and Maloney's (2008) argument that such interactive state transitions heighten a user's susceptibility to deep engagement within the game's environment.

Moreover, A. Knowlton's (2021) narrative analysis supports the game's effectiveness and engageability by concluding that its use of second-person narration and interactive choice empowers students to guide the story in ways that align with their own values, thereby enhancing narrative fidelity and increasing the likelihood of intertextual understanding and perceived credibility of the characters and central theme.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

The game delves into sensitive themes like racial injustice, historical trauma, and their intergenerational effects, encouraging players to reflect on how past events impact families and communities. While these topics are essential for fostering empathy, educators must handle discussions with care to ensure students feel supported and comfortable engaging with these challenging issues (Schrier et al., 2024).

Reviewer(s): Johannes Katsarov

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